

Lithuania | One Health Surveillance | Tickborne diseases

Background & objectives

- Review the legislation, data and information published on the websites of stakeholders related to tickborne diseases
- Improve the collaboration and data related to tickborne diseases sharing between different stakeholders
- Improve public tools about tickborne diseases and prevention
- Strengthen the core capacities of specialists involved in tickborne diseases

Outcomes & Impact

- A comprehensive analysis of the foodborne disease's surveillance data published on the websites NVSC has been carried out
- There is a public [map](#) on sites where patients contracted tick-borne encephalitis (TBE)
- An algorithm for tick collection methodology is developed, and one for Lyme disease surveillance and another for TBE surveillance are in draft form

Lessons learned

- One of the effective ways to inform and share information about TBE surveillance is to use interactive tools
- It is important to identify the stakeholders concerned accurately

Core messages

- Organize periodic meetings to discuss ongoing and planned activities
- Use interactive tools to share information about TBE with the general public and professionals